

D8.4: Promotional Video, second batch

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Revision history:

VERSION	DATE	Revised by	Reason
0.1	24/05/2024	Vana Stavridi	Preparation of the script
0.2	10/06/2024	Michael Bangrover, Alina Kadlubsky, Oliver Schreer	Comments on the 2st draft of the voice Over and visions
0.3	17/06/2024	NTUA team	Preparation of the 3rd draft (pre final version) of the video script by incorporating the partners' comments.
0.4	27/06/2024	Rigmor Baraas, Rose Bernabe	Comments on the prefinal version of video
1.0.	06/08/2023	NTUA team	Release the 2nd promotional video

Contents

1. Aim of the 2nd promotional video.....	5
2. Development process.....	5
3. Video design and format.....	7
4. Communication of the 2nd promotional video.....	11
5. Deviations from DoA	12

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1. Aim of the 2nd promotional video

As part of XR4Human's dissemination and communication activities, WP8 has collaborated with project partners and coordinators to produce the second promotional video. Aligned with the objectives outlined in the Grant Agreement, this video supports the project's broader efforts to increase visibility and raise awareness. Titled **XR4Human: Building Together – Current Engagement Activities and Results**, the video highlights ongoing engagement efforts and showcases key interim outcomes. Aimed at a diverse audience, it also serves as an invitation for stakeholders to join the project's two key communication platforms: the XR4Human Experience Library and the XR4Human Forum.

The video presents the basic aspects of the project, emphasizing its mission and key objectives to inform the broader public. It then transitions to showcase the project's key final outcomes, providing an early overview of these results and the ongoing activities.

2. Development process

The creation of the video was a collaborative effort, with significant input from various WPs. This input shaped both the content and narrative of the video, ensuring that the 2nd promotional video accurately represents the project's goals and impact on users' wellbeing.

The narrative was crafted by integrating key messages from each WP, highlighting the work carried out in XR4Human. Emphasis was given on the WPs that have already accomplished some of the main outcomes of the project, as well as on those that have developed tools and platforms for engagement activities.

To illustrate the development process of the promotional video, the following figures provide insight into both the initial design phase and the final phase. These visual elements demonstrate how feedback from various partners was gathered and incorporated into the final design of the video.

Script Template

Video Title	XR4Human: Engagement in Action or XR4Human: Building Together – Current Engagement activities and Results
Writer	Vana Stajvidi

Draft voice over (500-word script). Includes audio/visual suggestions.

WP	Scene	Script	Visual	Sound Effects
	1.	No voice over	Gradual appearance of the XR4HUMAN logo in the form of pixels which, as they are composed, will create the complete image of the logo. *Note: The colors and theme should match those of the XR4Human website (https://xr4human.eu/). The transitions between words and graphics should be a bit more interesting than just fading or sliding. More like, popping, growing, shrinking, and moving. 	Some minimal sounds or music.
	2.	No voice over	Title Text: XR4Human: Engagement in Action or XR4Human: Building Together – Current Engagement and Results We must add at this scene the acknowledgment of our funders in the following way: The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101070155 And with the addition of the EU flag in optimal quality: 	Some minimal sounds or music.
	3.	The power of extended Reality lies in its limitless potential for enhancing human experience. extended Reality creates and recreates reality, extends it, and bends it in a manner that was	* The following should be typed while is read: What are the risks of XR Technologies for users? (Here an icon could be inserted where it would show that someone is typing this question into Google search)	

		previously restricted to the world of science fiction. As with other emerging technologies, however, the use and eventual ubiquity of extended Reality technologies bring with them new risks and challenges, including those related to ethics, safety, privacy, security, and interoperability.	• And then could be appeared the results of this search: <i>Physical and mental health</i> <i>Diversity</i> <i>Inclusivity</i> <i>Abuse of power</i> <i>Accessibility issues</i> <i>Privacy, ownership, access, data issues</i> <i>Interoperability issues</i>	
	4.	These challenges, without proper oversight and governance, run the risk of compromising on basic European values of "inclusion, justice, solidarity, and non-discrimination.	An image like the below one, (1 st video, 1:46-1:57) in which the floating boxes will contain the following words: XR, governance, inclusion, justice, solidarity, and non-discrimination. 	
	5.	XR4Human aims to support European companies in leading the deployment, adoption, and acceptance of XR technologies by promoting ethical, equitable, inclusive, and human-centered practices. Simultaneously, it empowers citizens to make informed decisions about purchasing and using XR. XR4Human offers guidance through the European Code of Conduct for XR technologies, the Guidelines for Interoperability, and an educational toolbox, all complemented by tools to facilitate their uptake.	The boxes in the above image will be composed and create the XR4Human logo, as in the 1st video: 1:57-2:00 And then you can put an image with this content: European Code of Conduct for responsible XR Technologies, Interoperability Guidance Document and Educational toolbox, which will rotate like this: 	
WPS (Code of Conduct for XR technology)	6.	70-90 words (Describe its objectives and how it will promote ethical, equitable, inclusive, and human-centered XR):	If you have any suggestion for image, please paste it here:	

Figure 1: Document for Gathering Input from WP Members

WP4(Interoperability Guidance document)	7.	To optimally implement these principles, it is essential to consider the broader context of XR technologies. Our analysis indicates that maintaining interoperability involves ensuring smooth data exchange across different systems. This enables users to access, move, transact, and create in both digital and physical environments. To support this, XR4Human will create a Guidance document on interoperability. This document will list standards that XR technology developers and producers can reference when designing their products.	If you have any suggestion for image, please paste it here: 	
WP7(Rating system and educational Toolbox)	8.	Educational materials, categorized by user profiles, will be produced to ensure inclusiveness and usability. These materials will include three videos covering XR terminology, risks and challenges, and applications.	If you have any suggestion for image, please paste it here:	
	9.	(Transitional proposal with which the engagement activities will be introduced.)		
	10.	Additionally, to promote the ethical use of XR technologies, we will create a user-friendly rating system. This system will highlight standards for ethics, safety, security, privacy, and interoperability, making these criteria clear to end-users.	Please, put an image depicting a rating system.	
WP1(XR4Human Forum)	11.	The XR4Human European Forum serves as a virtual dialogue space for all relevant stakeholders, providing a platform to discuss ethical issues and gather cross-sectoral perspectives. This collaborative platform aims to create impactful outcomes by addressing concerns and promoting best practices in the		

		development and use of XR technologies.	 If you have any other suggestion for image, please paste it here.	
WP6(XR4Human Experience Library)	12.	XR4Human is inherently multidisciplinary and multi-stakeholder, and this is demonstrated in practice through two digital collaborative platforms: the XR4Human Experience Library and the XR4Human European Forum. The XR4Human Experience Library empowers the community to share their own XR experiences and commitment to best practices.	 If you have any other suggestion for image, please paste it here.	

Figure 2: Sample of Final Video Script with XR4Human Partners' Input on Narration and Visualization

3. Video Design and Format

The videos were crafted in alignment with the distinctive visual identity and branding of XR4Human. We consistently incorporated the project's official colors, fonts, and icons to ensure a cohesive and recognizable look. The project's visual identity, characterized by vibrant colors and imagery related to VR, AR, and XR technologies, was deliberately employed to make the content visually appealing and user-friendly. As a result, the video visuals harmonize with these key elements, maintaining a consistent and engaging aesthetic.

Below it is presented the video by showcasing some characteristic screen captures.

Figure 3: The first video's scene where the XR4Human parts of logo appears gradually in the form of pixels which come together to form the complete image.

Figure 4: The second video's scene where there is an acknowledgement of the XR4Human funders.

As the video progresses, we briefly showcase the potential of XR technologies, along with the emerging challenges and risks they bring, while showcasing our efforts to address them.

Figure 5 & 6: Video's scenes that reflect European values and showcase XR4Human's interventions to ensure their longevity regarding to the development of XR technologies.

Figure 7: Video's scene that illustrates the European XR Code of Conduct.

Figure 8: An illustration of what interoperability is and what the Interoperability Guidance Document (one of the XR4Human's outcomes) aims to achieve.

Figure 9: An overview of educational videos that will be produced.

Figure 10: Illustration of the rating system.

Next, as we move toward the end of the video, we introduce the project's two engagement platforms, XR4Human Experience Library and XR4Human Forum, inviting stakeholders to interact and share their perspectives with us.

Figure 11: XR4Human Experience Library' capture.

Figure 12: XR4Human Forum.

The closing scene informs viewers about the XR4Human Social Media accounts.

Figure 13: Closing scene of the XR4Human video.

3. Communication of the 2st promotional video

The video serves as an essential communication and dissemination tool to promote the XR4Human project, its objectives, and the key outcomes from the first and second period of the project. While the third promotional video will promote in details the findings and final outcomes of the project. The 2nd promotional video has already been published in XR4Human YouTube channels ([2nd promotional video](#)) and shared via project's LinkedIn and X (formerly Twitter) accounts. It will also be featured at the top of the XR4Human website and made available on the Zenodo platform. The WP8 has provided all the project partners with the video URL to facilitate its distribution through their networks including partners' social media accounts, etc. In addition, the video can be showcased at events and conferences, either embedded in presentations or displayed on laptops/screens, to highlight key objectives, ongoing engagement activities, and intermediate results.

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Deviations from DoA

No Deviations from DoA.

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